

CELL INTEGRATION

Enhanced energy density by using Si-Anodes

ELECTRODE MANUFACTURING:

POUCH CELL CHARACTERISATION:

SCALING TO 21700:

Lead:

VARTA

Partners:

BMW GROUP, ZSW, ARKEMA, JÜLICH Forschungszentrum, speira, virtual vehicle, CIRCUIT FOIL

Overall Goal

Manufacture newly developed electrodes and prototype cells and to assess their technical feasibility and electrochemical performance while considering their requirements on material and electrode level and in the formation procedure.

Cell Integration of Electrodes and Electrolytes in Pouch Cell Format

- Enhanced cycleability by varying different parameters:
 - Variation of Si content >> 70%
 - Improved Electrolyte
 - Modified Substrate
- Investigation of pre-compression and pure Si anode.

Progress of G-Si Composite by Using a High Si Content

Volume Expansion Pure Si Anode

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